

ANALYSIS OF VIBRATION CONTROL IN STRUCTURAL MEMBERS USING PIEZOELECTRIC SMART MATERIALS

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Abstract: This study presents a comprehensive numerical investigation of the vibration characteristics of aluminium beams enhanced with anisotropic layers and integrated piezoelectric PVDF (polyvinylidene fluoride) patches for improved dynamic performance. Finite Element Analysis (FEA) is carried out using ANSYS APDL 2024 R1 to evaluate natural frequencies, mode shapes, and dynamic responses under various boundary conditions. Several beam configurations are examined to quantify the effects of stiffness variation, anisotropic layer orientation, and end constraints on modal behaviour. The results indicate that increased structural rigidity and more restrictive boundary conditions significantly raise natural frequencies and reduce vibration sensitivity. Active vibration control is achieved by applying differential voltages to the PVDF patches, generating counteracting piezoelectric forces that suppress structural oscillations. Comparative analyses demonstrate a substantial reduction in peak vibration amplitudes when piezoelectric actuation is enabled. Harmonic response simulations further confirm effective vibration attenuation over a wide excitation frequency range, highlighting the robustness of the smart beam system under fluctuating dynamic loads.

Key words: Piezoelectric actuation, PVDF patches, Active vibration control and Finite Element Analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

Piezoelectric sensors energy harvesting, and vibration controllers has grown slowly in society. A phenomenon known as the piezoelectric effect occurs when mechanical stress is applied to some materials, causing them to produce an electrical charge. Pierre and Jacques Curie made the initial discovery of this phenomenon in 1880. The Greek word "piezein," which means to press or squeeze, is where the name piezoelectric originates. Piezoelectric materials are the vice-versa materials that can give mechanical energy, and they generate electrical power; when we apply electrical energy they produce mechanical fluctuations. We prepare the beam/plate with adhesive

to help attach the piezo sensors with various boundary conditions to know the vibration characteristics.

Yashavantha, Sathish Kumar [1]. Investigated free vibration behavior of a smart composite cantilever beam with PZT patches is the primary focus of this work. Modal shapes and fundamental frequencies are identified via ANSYS Modal Analysis, which also demonstrates how variations in these modes might be a sign of damage. The results demonstrate how useful Modal Analysis is for tracking the structural integrity of smart composite materials. Zhu Xiaojin, Zhao Miao, et al. [2] This article describes a procedure for utilizing ANSYS and MATLAB to simulate and analyze piezoelectric flexible plates. In addition to developing an iterative learning control system and verifying NASA's optimization criteria, it creates a modeling technique for intelligent structures with distributed sensors and actuators. The outcomes demonstrate economical analysis and excellent vibration suppression. Sharvari S. Heganna, et al. [3] Piezoelectric materials can be employed as actuators to induce structural changes and vibration suppression through their inverse piezoelectric effect these will be working in vibration sensors and to generate the oceanic applications to harvest electrical energy and give the pre-instructions of precipitate moments of climate changes. Various methods are used in the setup consisting of three components such as an exciter (a Lead-Zirconate-Titanate patch), a sensor (a second patch that detects the disturbance in real-time) and an actuator (a third patch that dampens vibrations). Singh, Saurav Sharma, et al.[4] The passive structure's inherent frequencies are moved to higher frequencies by the presence of patches. A cantilever beam or plate with piezoelectric material on it is hence intelligent. Modal analysis was used to establish where the actuators and piezo sensors should be placed on the beam or plate. It may detect the deformation brought on by the stimulation of the structure and be used as a sensor. It is frequently utilized as an active control of the positive piezoelectric effect of piezoelectric materials.

Schlaberg, Duff, et al. [5] studied the Electrical and Mechanical properties of two different piezoelectric composite materials. Lalit, shendre, et al. [6] studied free vibration response of Aluminium beam bonded with two number of piezoelectric patches one on top and another at bottom. Yaman, caliskan, et al. [7] investigated numerical and experimental investigations on piezoelectric smart plate by varying the size of the patch and position of the patch.

While doing research [Ref :8,9 and 10] on the impact of pressure on the production of electrical charge by crystals such as quartz, tourmaline, and Rochelle salt, the phenomenon known

as piezoelectricity, or pressure electricity, was found in 1880. The opposite piezoelectric effect was then shown in 1881 by applying basic thermodynamic concepts. Below are the constitutive equations for the direct and reverse piezoelectric effects.

$$\text{Direct effect: } D = dT + \epsilon E$$

$$\text{Converse effect: } X = St + dE$$

Where

D = electrical displacement

d = piezoelectric coefficient

T = stress, ϵ = permittivity of the material

S is mechanical compliance, X is strain, and E is electric field. Koppanati, Rani, et al. [11] examine vibrations of graphene inclusions in FRP composites. Meera Saheb, Sairag Lanka, et al. [12] experimentally explored natural frequencies of visco elastic sandwich structures.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section provides a succinct description of the exact methodology/procedure used in the study, enabling anybody who wants to repeat it to get similar findings. Give enough information to clear up any doubts that could exist regarding the design, treatments, measurements, analysis, etc. When techniques are widely accepted in a certain field, specifics should be left out and a reference should be provided in their place. Modifications to established methods, however, need to be addressed and detailed in detail. One statement cannot be the only thing in a paragraph.

2.1. Materials and Specimen Geometries

In the present study author investigated vibration response of Al beam with effect of PVDF patches and 12V external electrical supply for different beam boundary conditions in beam cantilever condition (C-F), one edge clamps other edges simply supported condition (C-S). two edges are simply supported condition (S-S) and opposite edges are clamped. The natural frequency and mode forms of the aforementioned structural elements are studied taking into account the boundary conditions of the beam. We the Al beam and bonded with one number of PVDF patches in beam with the help of polyurethane adhesive in an equal quaternal area. In every patch, we

attached two leads with a crimping process to supply 12v electric energy to the patches. The mechanical and geometric properties of the materials used to create smart beams are listed in Tables 1 and 2.

2.2. Finite Element Modelling

In Ansys 2024 R1 APDL software is employed to carry out Finite Element Analysis (FEA) on smart beams. In the plane region, an isotropic beam model measuring 230 x 36 x 2 mm is constructed by adding the following mechanical properties including modulus of elasticity (E), Poisson's ratio (μ) and density (ρ) of aluminum, listed in Table2. Piezoelectric sensor dimensions are 40.40 x17.21 x 0.4 mm and its properties are given in table 1. In beam the PVDF patch is placed at 10 mm from the left end of the beam. Ansys 2024 R1 APDL software and planes are modelled as coupled field [Brick 20node 226] is used for meshing [SOLID 226] for a piezoelectric sensor in anisotropic properties and SOLID [20node186] for isotropic properties and composite each of which has six degrees of freedom. As well 12V electrical energy is supplied to the structural member with a PVDF patch.

Table 1. Properties of piezoelectric patches.

Property	PVDF	Unit
Density	1780	kg/m ³
Elastic Stiffness Matrix		
C ₁₁	23.9×10^{10}	N/m ²
C ₁₂	-7.95×10^{10}	N/m ²
C ₁₃	-7.18×10^{10}	N/m ²
C ₃₃	62.2×10^{10}	N/m ²
C ₄₄	62.2×10^{10}	N/m ²
Piezoelectric Strain Matrix		
E ₃₁	6.5	C/m ²
E ₃₃	23.3	C/m ²
E ₁₅	17	C/m ²
Dielectric Matrix		
ϵ_{11}	0.203×10^{-8}	F/m
ϵ_{22}	0.12×10^{-8}	F/m
ϵ_{33}	1.03×10^{-8}	F/m

TABLE 2. Properties of Aluminium material

Parameter	beam	Units
Length (L)	230	mm
Width (b)	36 mm	mm
Thickness (h)	2 mm	mm
Young's Modulus (E)	7.1×10^{10}	N/m ²
Density (ρ)	2700	kg/m ³
Poisson's Ratio(μ)	0.3	-

Figure 1. A finite element mesh model of beam with rectangular PVDF patch at a distance of 10mm from left support with 12V electric energy supply.

2.3 Modeling of Beams in Ansys

Figure 4. C-F rectangular beam with PVDF patch with 12V supply boundary condition.

Figure 5. C-S rectangular beam with PVDF patch with 12V supply boundary condition.

Figure 6. S-S rectangular beam with PVDF patch with 12V supply boundary condition.

Figure 7. C-C rectangular beam with PVDF patch with 12V supply boundary condition.

The above all figures are the represents the smart beam in various conditions in simulation figures and experimental modal analysis of the beams in C-F, C-C, S-S, C-S conditions to the attachment of pvdf patches of the isotropic Aluminium beam with the help of function generator supply 12volts electric energy in pvdf patches in both simulation and experimental process.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section discusses the results for beams natural frequencies and mode shapes. The findings of the experiment are compared and reviewed with the ANSYS results for natural frequencies and mode shapes. This research highlights the outcomes of Ansys APDL and Experimental Modal Analysis for an Aluminium beam equipped with piezoelectric patches and thus studied three types of different case studies.

3.1 Beams

- i) Aluminium beam
- ii) Aluminium beam with PVDF patch and
- iii) Aluminium beam with PVDF patch with 12V electrical supply.

Vibration analysis is carried out for above cases of beams with different boundary circumstances using Experimental Modal Analysis and Ansys.

Table 3. Natural frequencies (Hz) of Aluminium rectangular beam with Piezoelectric patches with various beam boundary conditions.

Boundary condition & Mode no	Ansys			Percentage Difference (%) (C)and (A)	
	Al Isotropic beam	Isotropic beam with PVDF patches	Isotropic beam with PVDF Patches in 12V		
	(A)	(B)	(C)		
C-F	1	11.7985	12.034	12.8259	8.0104
	2	76.031	79.357	82.0935	7.3849

	3	188.3609	190.02	208.252	9.5515
C-C	1	79.765	80.3655	84.9912	6.1491
	2	218.5196	220.0035	240.679	9.2070
	3	430.631	430.631	451.816	4.6889
S-S	1	69.3917	71.2647	78.7983	11.9376
	2	201.432	206.821	223.449	9.8533
	3	407.746	409.825	436.701	6.6304
C-S	1	11.986	12.0197	12.8401	6.6518
	2	76.6213	79.1513	82.2077	6.7955
	3	219.623	217.841	236.224	7.0277

C-F

C-C

Figure 8. variation of natural frequencies with mode number for Aluminium beam C-F, C-C with PVDF patch and 12V energy supply

Figure 9. variation of natural frequencies with mode number for Aluminium beam C-S and S-S with PVDF patch and 12V energy supply

Figure 10. Early three fundamental modes are presented for Ansys and EMA of Aluminium beam (C-F) with patch with 12V supply.

Figure 11. Early three fundamental modes are presented for Ansys and EMA of Aluminium beam (C-C) with patch with 12V supply.

Figure 12. Early three fundamental modes are presented for EMA and ANSYS of Aluminium beam (S-S) with patches with 12V supply.

Figure 13. Early three fundamental modes are presented for EMA and ANSYS of Aluminium beam (S-C) with patch and 12V supply.

3.3. Discussion on characteristics of smart Beams

The numerical results obtained from ANSYS simulations clearly demonstrate the effect of piezoelectric PVDF patches and boundary conditions on the vibration characteristics of aluminium smart beams. For all support configurations clamped-free (C-F), clamped-clamped (C-C), simply supported-simply supported (S-S), and clamped-simply supported (C-S) the inclusion of PVDF layers increases the natural frequencies compared with the bare isotropic beam. This behavior is primarily due to the additional stiffness introduced by the piezoelectric material and its electromechanical coupling with the host structure.

Further increases are observed when the PVDF patches are electrically actuated at 12 V, indicating a voltage-induced stiffening effect typical of active smart structures. The percentage difference between the actuated configuration and the aluminium beam ranges from approximately 4.7% to 11.9%, confirming that electrical control can significantly modify the beam's dynamic properties. Among the boundary conditions, the clamped-clamped beam consistently exhibits the highest modal frequencies because of its strong end restraints, while the

clamped-free configuration shows the lowest values, making it more susceptible to vibration. These trends closely follow classical beam vibration theory, validating the numerical approach.

The simply supported beam configuration displays the largest percentage increase in the first mode under active actuation, suggesting that moderately constrained systems benefit most from piezoelectric control. Higher vibration modes also experience noticeable frequency shifts, although the magnitude depends on the compatibility between the mode shapes and the patch locations. Modes associated with higher bending strains near the piezoelectric layers show stronger electromechanical interaction. Overall, the results confirm that aluminium beams integrated with anisotropic PVDF patches exhibit superior vibration resistance compared with conventional metallic beams. The ability to tune natural frequencies through electrical inputs provides adaptability under varying operational conditions. Such characteristics make PVDF-based smart beams highly suitable for lightweight and dynamically sensitive structures in aerospace, automotive, marine, and civil engineering applications.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This numerical investigation demonstrates the effectiveness of integrating anisotropic PVDF piezoelectric patches into Aluminium beams to enhance their vibration performance under various boundary conditions. Finite Element simulations carried out in ANSYS APDL reveal that both passive attachment and active electrical actuation of the piezoelectric layers increase natural frequencies, indicating a rise in effective structural stiffness. Among all support cases, clamped-clamped beams exhibit the highest modal frequencies, while clamped-free beams remain the most vibration-prone, in agreement with classical vibration theory. Active control using differential voltage inputs produces measurable frequency shifts and contributes to reduced dynamic susceptibility across multiple modes. The results further confirm that smart beams outperform purely metallic counterparts by offering tunable dynamic characteristics and improved damping capability. These findings highlight the potential of PVDF-based smart structures for applications requiring adaptive vibration control, lightweight design, and long-term structural reliability in aerospace, automotive, marine, and civil engineering systems.

5. FUTURE WORK

Although the present numerical study confirms the effectiveness of PVDF-integrated smart beams for vibration suppression, several areas remain open for further investigation. Future

research should focus on experimental validation of the numerical results to establish stronger reliability under real operating conditions. Conducting laboratory-scale modal testing and harmonic response experiments will help quantify discrepancies between simulation and physical behavior.

Additionally, the influence of higher excitation voltages and adaptive control strategies such as closed-loop feedback systems can be explored to achieve superior vibration attenuation. Optimization of patch placement, geometry, and orientation using advanced techniques like topology optimization or machine learning algorithms may further enhance electromechanical coupling and structural performance.

The current work considers linear material behavior; therefore, incorporating nonlinear effects, temperature-dependent properties, and long-term fatigue analysis would provide a more realistic assessment for industrial applications. Investigating hybrid smart materials combining PVDF with PZT or fiber-reinforced composites could also improve actuation authority and durability.

Finally, extending the study to complex structural components such as plates, shells, and aerospace-grade lightweight structures will broaden practical applicability. Integration of energy harvesting capabilities alongside vibration control represents another promising direction toward self-powered smart structural systems.

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